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SPATIAL DATA STRUCTURES

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Annotation: *This article describes the types of data used in the process of data processing in geographic information systems and their use, as well as the structure of this data.*

Key words: *Raster data structure, vector data structure, basic spatial data analysis, encoding data structure, topological data structure*

ПРОСТРАНСТВЕННЫЕ СТРУКТУРЫ ДАННЫХ

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Аннотация: *В данной статье описаны типы данных, используемые в процессе обработки данных в геоинформационных системах и их использование, а также структура этих данных.*

Ключевые слова: *структура растровых данных, структура векторных данных, базовый анализ пространственных данных, структура данных кодирования, топологическая структура данных.*

Structures that provide information required for computer to reconstruct spatial data model in digital form are defined as spatial data structure. Many GIS software have specific capabilities for storing and manipulating attributes data in

addition to spatial information. However, basic spatial data structures in GIS are mainly vector and raster.

Raster Data Structure

Raster or grid data structure refers to the storage of the raster data for data processing and analysis by the computer. There are mainly three commonly used data structures such as cell-by-cell encoding, run-length encoding, and quadtree

Cell-By-Cell Encoding Data Structure

This is the simplest raster data structure and is characterised by subdividing a geographic space into grid cells. Each pixel or grid cell contains a value. A grid matrix and its cell values for a raster are arranged into a file by row and column. Fig.1 shows the cell-by-cell encoding data structure. Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) are the best examples for this method of data structure. In Fig.1, value 1 represents the gray cells and 0 has no data. This cell-by-cell encoding method can also be used for storage of data in satellite images. Most of satellite images consist of multispectral bands and each pixel in a satellite image has more than one value. Mainly three formats such as Band Sequential (BSQ), Band Interleaved by Lines (BIL), and Band Interleaved by Pixels (BIP) are used to store data in a multiband/multispectral imagery.

Fig.1 : Cell-by-cell encoding data structure

Run-Length Encoding Data Structure

Run-Length Encoding (RLE) algorithm was developed to handle the problem that a grid often contains redundant or missing data. When the raster data contains more missing data, the cell-by-cell encoding method cannot be suggested. In RLE method, adjacent cells along a row with the same value are treated as a group called a run. If a whole row has only one class, it is stored as the class and the same attributes are kept without change. Instead of repeatedly storing the same value for each cell, the value is stored once together with the

number of the cells that makes the run. Fig.2 explains the run-length encoding structure of a polygon. In the figure, the starting cell and the end cell of the each row denote the length of group and is generally called as run. RLE data compression method is used in many GIS packages and in standard image formats.

Fig. 2: Run-length encoding data structure

Quadtree Data Structure

To compress the data as well as to save the space in original grid, quad tree data structure can be used (Fig. 3). A quadtree works by dividing a grid into four quadrants for the available data. The available data quadrant is again split into four half-size quadrants and so on until the individual pixel is reached. The attribute data for all the pixels of the quadrant remains the same even if it is divided.

Fig. 3: Quadtree data structure

Vector Data Structure

As you know description of geographical phenomena explained in the form of point, line, or polygons is called as vector data structure. Vector data structures are now widely used in GIS and computer cartography. This data structure has an advantage in deriving information from digitisation, and is more exact in representation of complex features such as administration boundaries, land parcels, etc. In early GIS, vector files were simply lines and were having only starting and ending points. The vector file consists of a few long lines, many short lines, or even a mix of the two. The files are generally written in a binary or ASCII (American Standard Code for Information Interchange) code which refers to a set of codes used to represent alpha numerical characters in computer data processing. Therefore, a computer programmer needs to follow the line from one place to another in the file to enter the data in system. This unstructured vector data are called as cartographic spaghetti. Vector data in the spaghetti data model may not be usable by GIS. However, most of the systems still use this basic data structure because of their standard format (e.g., mapping agency's standard linear format).

To express the spatial relationships more accurately between the features, the concept of topology has evolved. Topology can explain the spatial relationships of adjacent, connectivity and containment between spatial features. Topological data are useful for detecting and correcting digitising errors e.g., two streams do not connect perfectly at an intersection point. Therefore, topology is necessary for carrying out some types of spatial analysis such as network and proximity.

There are commonly two data structures used in vector GIS data storage viz. topological and non-topological structures.

Let us now discuss about the two types of data structure.

a) Topological Data Structure

Topologic data structure is often referred to as an intelligent data structure because spatial relationships between geographic features are easily derived when using them. Because of this reason topological vector data structure is important in undertaking complex data analysis. In a topological data structure, lines cannot overlap without a node whereas lines can overlap without nodes in a non-topological data structure (e.g., spaghetti).

The arc-node topological data structure is now used in most of the systems. In the arc-node data structure, the arc is used for the data storage and it also works when it is needed to reconstruct a polygon. In file of arcs, point data is stored and linked to the arc file. Arc is a line segment and its structure is given in Fig. 4. Node refers to the end points of the line segment. The arc has information not only

related to that particular arc but also to its neighbours in geographic space. It includes the arc number of the next connecting arc and the polygon number i.e. A: the left polygon (PL) and B: the right polygon (PR). The arc forms areas or polygons, and the polygon identifier number is the key for constructing a polygon. Some important vector data structures are such as Topologically Integrated Geographic Encoding and Referencing (TIGER) and Coverage Data Structure.

Fig. 4: Topological structure of the arc

b) Topologically Integrated Geographic Encoding and Referencing (TIGER)

It is an early application of topology in preparing geospatial data created by US Bureau of Census as an improvement to the Geographic Base File/Dual Independent Map Encoding (GBF/DIME) data structure. This data structure or format was used in the 2000 census by US Bureau of the Census. In the TIGER database, points are called 0-cells, lines 1-cells, and areas 2-cells

(Fig. 5). Each 1-cell represents a direct line which starts from one point and ending at another point. The line comprises both sides of the data. Each 2 and 0-cells share of the information of the 1-cells associated with it. The main advantage of this data structure is that the user can easily identify an address on either the right side or the left side of a street or road.

Fig. 5: Topology in TIGER database

c) Coverage Data Structure

Coverage data structure was practised by many GIS companies like ESRI, in their software packages in 1980s to separate GIS from CAD (Computer Aided Design). A coverage data structure is a topology based vector data structure that can be a point, line or polygon coverage. A point is a simple spatial entity which can be represented with topology. The point coverage data structure contains feature identification numbers (ID) and pairs of x, y coordinates, as for example A (2, 4) (Fig.6). Data structure of line coverage is represented in Fig.7. The starting point of the arc is called from node (F-Node) and where it ends to node (T-Node). The arc-node list represents the x, y coordinates of the nodes and the other points (vertices) that generate each arc. For example, arc C consists of three line segments comprising F-Node at (7, 2), the T-Node at (2, 6) and vertex at (5, 2).

Fig.1 shows the relationship between polygons and arcs (polygon/arc list), arcs and their left and right polygons (left poly/right poly list), and the nodes and vertices (arc-coordinate list). Polygon 'a' is created with arcs A,B,G,H and I. Polygon 'c' surrounded by polygon 'a' is an isolated polygon and consists of only one arc, i.e. 8. 'o' is the universal polygon which covers outside the map area. Arc A is a directed line from node 1 to node 2 and has polygon 'o' as the polygon on the left and polygon 'a' as right polygon. The common boundary between two polygons (o and a) is stored in the arc-coordinate list once only, and is not duplicated.

Fig. 6: Point coverage data structure

d) Non-Topological Data Structure

Vector data structure that is common among GIS software is the Computer Aided Design (CAD) data structure. Drawing Exchange Format (DXF) is used in

the CAD package (e.g., AutoCAD) for transferring of the data files. DXF does not support topology and arrange the data as individual layers.

This structure consists of listing elements, not features, defined by strings of vertices, to define geographic features, e.g., points, lines, or areas. There is considerable redundancy with this data model since the boundary segment between two polygons will be stored twice, once for each feature. This format allows user to draw each layer by using different line symbols, colours and texts. In this structure, polygons are independent and difficult to answer about the adjacency of features. The CAD vector model lacks the definition of spatial relationships between features that is defined by the topological data model.

Since 1990s almost all commercial GIS packages such as ArcGIS, MapInfo, Geomedia have adopted non-topological data structure. Shape file (.shp) is a standard non-topological data format used in GIS packages. In ArcInfo coverage, the geometry of shape file is stored into two extension types such as .shp and .shx. Shape file (.shp) stores the feature geometry and .shx file maintains the spatial index of the feature geometry. The advantage of non-topological data structure, i.e. shape file, lies in quick display on the system than the topological data. Many software packages such as ArcGIS, MapInfo uses the .shp file format.

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